

4-Quinazolones. Part VII. Synthesis of some Quinazolin-4(3H)-ones

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The synthesis of 7-hydroxy-8-methoxy-(VI) and 7,8-dimethoxy-2-methyl-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (VII); 7-hydroxy-8-methoxy-(IX) and 7,8-dimethoxy-2-n-butyl-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (X); 6,7-dimethoxy-2-methyl-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (XVII) and 6,7-dimethoxy-2,3-diphenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (XVIII) is described.

4-Quinazolones with substituents in the benzene ring are sparsely described in the literature. In a synthetic project some such hitherto unreported quinazolones were required and in this communication their preparation is described. 7-Hydroxy-8-methoxy-2-methyl-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (VI), 7,8-dimethoxy-2-methyl-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (VII), 7-hydroxy-8-methoxy-2-n-butyl-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (IX) and 7,8-dimethoxy-2-n-butyl-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (X) were obtained from the common starting material 4-benzyloxy-3-methoxy-2-aminobenzoic acid¹ (I), whereas 6,7-dimethoxy-2-methyl-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (XVII) and 6,7-dimethoxy-2,3-diphenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (XVIII) were secured from 3,4-dimethoxy-6-nitrobenzoic acid² (XI).

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| I : R = NH ₂ | IV | V : R = CH ₂ Ph; R ₁ = CH ₃ |
| II : R = NHCOCH ₃ | | VI : R = H; R ₁ = CH ₃ |
| III : R = NHCO.C ₄ H ₉ (n) | | VII : R = R ₁ = CH ₃ |
| | | VIII : R = CH ₂ Ph; R ₁ = C ₄ H ₉ (n) |
| | | IX : R = H; R ₁ = C ₄ H ₉ (n) |
| | | X : R = CH ₃ ; R ₁ = C ₄ H ₉ (n) |

Acetylation of 4-benzyloxy-3-methoxy-2-aminobenzoic acid¹ (I) followed by interaction of the resulting 4-benzyloxy-3-methoxy-2-acetamidobenzoic acid (II) with aniline in the presence of phosphorus trichloride in boiling toluene furnished 7-benzyloxy-8-methoxy-2-methyl-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (V). This quinazolone was also obtained in an

1. Part IV. V. Srivastava and D. N. Chaudhury, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **46**.
2. Part VI. S. K. P. Sinha and D. N. Chaudhury, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, in press.

alternative way. I when refluxed with acetic anhydride gave 7-benzyloxy-8-methoxy-2-methyl-4H-3,1-benzoxazin-4-one (IV) which on heating with aniline was converted into V. The oxazine IV could easily be hydrolysed with water to II. Debenzylation of V by catalytic hydrogenation with palladised charcoal afforded 7-hydroxy-8-methoxy-2-methyl-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (VI). On methylation with diazomethane VI was transformed into its methyl ether, 7,8-dimethoxy-2-methyl-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (VII).

When an ethereal suspension of the amino acid (I) was acylated with n-valeroyl chloride in the presence of pyridine 4-benzyloxy-3-methoxy-2-n-valeroylaminobenzoic acid (III) was obtained. It was converted into 7-benzyloxy-8-methoxy-2-n-butyl-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (VIII) by the action of aniline and phosphorus trichloride in boiling toluene. VIII was debenzylated by catalytic hydrogenation to give 7-hydroxy-8-methoxy-2-n-butyl-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (IX) which with diazomethane yielded 7,8-dimethoxy-2-n-butyl-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (X).

3,4-Dimethoxy-6-aminobenzoic acid (XII), obtained by the reduction of 3,4-dimethoxy-6-nitrobenzoic acid² (XI) with sodium dithionite, on treatment with refluxing acetic anhydride or with benzoyl chloride in the presence of pyridine afforded respectively 3,4-dimethoxy-6-acetamidobenzoic and 3,4-dimethoxy-6-benzamido-benzoic acids (XIII and XIV). Treatment with aniline and phosphorus trichloride in boiling toluene converted XIII and XIV into 6,7-dimethoxy-2-methyl-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (XVII) and 6,7-dimethoxy-2,3-diphenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (XVIII). These quinazolones were also secured by an *alternative* route. The acids XIII and XIV, with boiling acetic anhydride, furnished respectively 6,7-dimethoxy-2-methyl-4H-3,1-benzoxazin-4-one (XV) and 6,7-dimethoxy-2-phenyl-4H-3,1-benzoxazin-4-one (XVI) which on interaction with hot aniline yielded the corresponding quinazolones XVII and XVIII.

Walker³ had earlier reported the preparation of the benzoxazine XV and the acetamido acid XIII by a route different from the one we adopted. 3,4-Dimethoxy-6-nitrophenylacetic acid when refluxed with acetic anhydride formed 6,7-dimethoxy-2-methyl-4H-3,1-benzoxazin-4-one (XV) which, on hydrolysis, yielded 3,4-dimethoxy-6-acetamidobenzoic acid (XIII).

EXPERIMENTAL

All m.p.s are uncorrected. Light petroleum used had b.p. 60-80°.

3. G. N. Walker, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 77, 6698.

4-Benzylloxy-3-methoxy-2-acetamidobenzoic acid (II) :- A mixture of I¹ (24 g.) and acetic anhydride (60 ml.) was refluxed for 4 hr., poured into ice-water (ca. 1 litre) and left overnight. The off-white lumps of solid which separated were collected, triturated with water, filtered, washed thoroughly with water and dried. The solid was heated under reflux with a small amount of benzene (ca. 75 ml.), cooled, filtered and washed with cold benzene to give almost colorless II (24 g.; 86.6%), m.p. 170-171°. It was used as such for the next operation. A sample twice crystallised from aq. dioxan furnished the analytical specimen as irregular colorless prisms, m.p. 171-172°. (Found : C, 64.5; H, 5.2. C₁₇H₁₇NO₅ requires C, 64.7; H, 5.4%).

7-Benzylloxy-8-methoxy-2-methyl-4H-3,1-benzoxazin-4-one (IV) :- A mixture of the *amino acid* (I; 8.6 g.) and acetic anhydride (20 ml.) was refluxed for 4 hr. Acetic anhydride (10 ml.) was then distilled off under reduced pressure and the residual solution on cooling in ice-bath deposited IV as colorless felted needles which were collected and washed with dry light petroleum. Yield 5.5 g.; 58.7%; m.p. 112-113°, with previous sintering at 100°. An analytical sample recrystallised from acetic anhydride did not raise the m.p. (Found : C, 68.4; H, 5.2; N, 5.0. C₁₇H₁₅O₄N requires C, 68.6; H, 5.0; N, 4.7%).

A solution of IV (1 g.) in hot acetic acid (2 ml.) poured into ice-water and the precipitate that separated was collected, dried and washed with boiling benzene. It was crystallised from dioxan to afford pure II as colorless prisms, m.p. and mixed m.p. 171-172°.

7-Benzylloxy-8-methoxy-2-methyl-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (V) :- *Method (a)*. A mixture of II (46 g.; 0.146 mole), aniline (13.8 ml.; 0.146 mole) and toluene (350 ml.) was treated dropwise with PCl₃ (4.27 ml.; 0.0486 mole) in toluene (15 ml.), and refluxed for 1 hr. The cooled reaction mixture was filtered, the precipitate washed with ether and dried. After triturating with dil. aq. NaOH it was filtered, washed thoroughly with water and crystallised from alcohol to give V as colorless shining flakes (42 g.; 77.3%), m.p. 157-158°. (Found : C, 74.3; H, 5.6; N, 7.8. C₂₃H₂₀N₂O₃ requires C, 74.2; H, 5.3; N, 7.5%).

Method (b). A mixture of the benzoxazine (IV, 2.97 g.; 0.01 mole) and aniline (0.94 ml.; 0.01 mole) was heated with occasional shaking in an oil-bath at 150-155° for 1 hr. On cooling, a hard glass like solid was obtained. It was dissolved in hot glacial acetic acid, the solution poured into ice-water and the solid which separated was filtered, washed with dil. NaOH and water. Recrystallisation from alcohol afforded V as colorless shining flakes (1.8 g.; 48%), m.p. 157-158°, undepressed on admixture with the sample obtained by method (a).

7-Hydroxy-8-methoxy-2-methyl-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (VI) :— A solution of V (10 g.) in glacial acetic acid (65 ml.) containing Pd-C catalyst (1 g.; 10%) was hydrogenated at room temperature until the theoretical amount of hydrogen absorbed. The solution was filtered, most of the acetic acid distilled off and the concentrated solution treated with ice-water when solid precipitated out. It was filtered, washed with water and dried in an exiccator. It was crystallised from benzene to give VI as rectangular plates (6.6 g.; 82%), m.p. 183-184°. (Found : C, 68.2; H, 5.2; N, 9.7. C₁₆H₁₄N₂O₃ requires C, 68.08; H, 4.9; N, 9.9%).

7,8-Dimethoxy-2-methyl-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (VII) :- A solution of the hydroxyquinazolone (VI, 0.5 g.) in ethanol (25 ml.) was treated at 0° with ethereal diazomethane (25 ml.) (from 2.5 g. N-nitrosomethyl urea) and left overnight at room temperature. Evaporation of the solvent left a colorless gum which solidified on treatment with a little benzene. The solid was filtered, washed with benzene and crystallised from isopropanol to furnish VII as colorless long rectangular rods (0.35 g.; 66%), m.p. 178-179°. (Found : C, 69.0; H, 5.6; N, 9.7. $C_{17}H_{16}O_3N_2$ requires C, 68.9; H, 5.4; N, 9.4%).

4-Benzoyloxy-3-methoxy-2-n-valeroylaminobenzoic acid (III) :- A suspension of I (5.8 g.) in dry ether (50 ml.) and pyridine (1.7 ml.) was treated with n-valeroyl chloride (2.6 g.) in dry ether (50 ml.) and left overnight. The ethereal solution was filtered from unreacted amino acid (I; 2 g.), the filtrate washed with water (3 × 30 ml.) and dried (Na_2SO_4). Evaporation of the solvent left an oil which was taken up in the minimum volume of benzene and treated with petroleum ether to give a colorless precipitate. Crystallisations from ethyl acetate-light petroleum afforded III as colorless felted needles (2 g.; 38%), m.p. 142-143°. (Found : C, 67.5; H, 6.7; N, 4.1. $C_{20}H_{23}NO_5$ requires C, 67.2; H, 6.4; N, 3.9%).

7-Benzoyloxy-8-methoxy-2-n-butyl-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (VIII) : A mixture of III (2.0 g.), toluene (30 ml.) and aniline (0.56 ml.) was treated dropwise with PCl_5 (0.2 ml.) and gently refluxed for 4 hr. when a clear solution was obtained. It was concentrated to a small bulk (ca. 10 ml.) and cooled. The colorless needles which started separating multiplied with the addition of petroleum ether (30 ml.); these were filtered, washed with petroleum ether, air-dried and triturated with 2N aq. Na_2CO_3 . It was again filtered, washed with water and air-dried. Recrystallisations from ethyl acetate-light petroleum afforded VIII as silky felted needles (1.6 g.; 68.9%), m.p. 205-206° with previous sintering at 204°. (Found : C, 75.5; H, 6.4; N, 6.9. $C_{26}H_{26}N_2O_3$ requires C, 75.3; H, 6.2; N, 6.7%).

7-Hydroxy-8-methoxy-2-n-butyl-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (IX) : A solution of VIII (1.5 g.) in glacial acetic acid (40 ml.) containing palladised charcoal (0.1 g.; 10%) was hydrogenated at room temperature until the theoretical amount of hydrogen absorbed. The solution was filtered and the filtrate concentrated to a small bulk (ca. 10 ml.), cooled and diluted with water (50 ml.) to give a colorless solid. It was filtered, washed with water and dissolved in the minimum volume of 2N. aq. NaOH. It was again filtered from insoluble impurities and the filtrate on acidification with acetic acid precipitated a colorless solid which was crystallised from ethyl acetate to afford IX as tiny colorless needles (0.8 g.; 68%), m.p. 203-204°. (Found : C, 70.5; H, 6.3; N, 8.4. $C_{19}H_{20}O_3N_2$ requires C, 70.3; H, 6.1; N, 8.6%).

7,8-Dimethoxy-2-n-butyl-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (X) :- A solution of IX (0.5 g.) in ethanol (20 ml.) was treated at 0° with ethereal diazomethane (from 2.5 g. N-nitrosomethyl urea) and left overnight. Evaporation of the solvent left a crystalline residue which was crystallised from benzene to furnish X as very long colorless rods (0.35 g.; 66%), m.p. 175-176°. (Found : C, 71.3; H, 6.8; N, 8.1. $C_{20}H_{22}N_2O_3$ requires C, 71.0; H, 6.5; N, 8.2%).

3,4-Dimethoxy-6-aminobenzoic acid (XII) :- Sodium dithionite (34.8 g.) was added in portions, with stirring, to a solution of 3,4-dimethoxy-6-nitrobenzoic acid³ (XI; 11.35 g.)

in aq. KOH (100 ml.; 10%) at 70-80° in the course of 0.5 hr., during which period the temperature was not allowed to rise above 80°. The reaction solution was cooled and acidified with conc. HCl (congo red) to precipitate the *amino acid* XII. It was filtered, washed with water, and dried in an exiccator. Yield 8.5 g.; m.p. 135-136°. It was used as such for the next operation. Crystallisation from ethyl acetate-light petroluem afforded the analytical specimen, m.p. 136-137°. (Found : C, 54.5; H, 5.7; N, 7.3. $C_9H_{11}O_4N$ requires, C, 54.8, H, 5.5; N, 7.1%).

3,4-Dimethoxy-6-acetamidobenzoic acid (XIII) :- The amino acid (XII; 1.97 g.) was refluxed with acetic anhydride (10 ml.) for 15 min. and left overnight. It was poured into crushed ice and the off-white precipitate that separated was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from dil. methanol or ethyl acetate to furnish XIII as colorless needles (2 g.; 88%), m.p. 224-225° (lit.⁴ m.p. 223.5-224.5°).

6,7-Dimethoxy-2-methyl-4H-3,1-benzoxazin-4-one (XV) :- The amino acid (XII; 1.97 g.) was refluxed with acetic anhydride (5 ml.) for 1 hr. and on cooling the clear solution deposited colorless needles which were filtered and washed with ether. Yield 1.1 g. (50%), m.p. 184-185° (lit.⁵ m.p. 186-187°).

A solution of the benzoxazine (XV, 0.3 g.) in hot acetic anhydride was poured into crushed ice, the solid that separated was filtered, washed with water and dried in an exiccator. Crystallisation from dil. methanol or ethyl acetate gave XIII, m.p. and mixed m.p. 224-225°.

3,4-Dimethoxy-6-benzamidobenzoic acid (XIV) :- The amino acid (XII; 1 g.), benzoyl chloride (0.75 ml.), dry benzene (15 ml.) and a few drops of pyridine were gently refluxed for 4 hr. On cooling a solid separated, which was filtered, washed with a little cold benzene and crystallised from a large volume of ethanol to give XIV as colorless needles (0.9 g.; 60%), m.p. 220-221°. (Found : C, 63.9; H, 5.2; N, 4.9. $C_{16}H_{15}O_5N$ requires C, 63.7; H, 4.9; N, 4.6%).

6,7-Dimethoxy-2-phenyl-4H-3,1-benzoxazin-4-one (XVI) :- XIV (3 g.) was refluxed with acetic anhydride (5 ml.) for 15 min. and left overnight. The crystals which separated were filtered, washed with ether and recrystallised from acetic anhydride to furnish XVI as colorless needles (1.7 g.; 60%), m.p. 203-204°. (Found : C, 67.5; H, 4.8; N, 4.8. $C_{16}H_{13}O_4N$ requires C, 67.8; H, 4.5; N, 4.9%).

A solution of XVI in hot acetic anhydride was poured into ice-water and the precipitate that separated, on crystallisation from ethanol, afforded XIV, m.p. and mixed m.p. 220-221°.

6,7-Dimethoxy-2-methyl-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (XVII) :- *Method* (a). A mixture of XIII (2.39 g.; 0.01 mole), aniline (0.93 ml.; 0.01 mole) and toluene (15 ml.) was treated dropwise with PCl_3 (0.3 ml.; 0.0033 mole) and heated under reflux at 110-120° (oil-bath) for 4 hr. The solid which separated on cooling, was filtered, washed with ether, dried and triturated with 10% aq. Na_2CO_3 . It was again filtered, washed with water and crystallised from ethanol to afford XVII (2.37 g.; 80%) as colorless tiny needles, m.p. 247-248°. (Found : C, 69.1; H, 5.6; N, 9.7. $C_{17}H_{16}O_3N_2$ requires C, 68.9; H, 5.4; N, 9.4%).

Method (b). The benzoxazine (XV, 2.2 g.) and aniline (0.93 ml.) was heated at 190-195° (oil-bath) for 1 hr. and left overnight. The solid reaction product was extracted with boiling benzene, filtered and the filtrate evaporated to dryness. The solid residue on several recrystallisations from ethanol gave XVII as colorless tiny needles (0.8 g.; 25%), m.p. and mixed m.p. 247-248°.

6,7-Dimethoxy-2,3-diphenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (XVIII) :- Method (a). A mixture of XIV (3 g.; 0.01 mole), and aniline (0.93 ml.; 0.01 mole) in toluene (15 ml.) was treated dropwise with PCl_3 (0.3 ml.; 0.0033 mole) and refluxed for 4 hr. The reaction mixture was worked up as in method (a) for the preceding compound to afford a solid which on several recrystallisations from aq. methanol furnished XVIII as clusters of colorless needles (1.8 g.; 50%), m.p. 247-248°. (Found : C, 73.8; H, 5.3; N, 8.0. $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_3\text{N}_2$ requires C, 73.7; H, 5.0; N, 7.8%).

Method (b). The benzoxazine (XVI; 2.83 g.) and aniline (0.93 ml.) was heated at 250-260° (oil-bath) for 2 hr. and left overnight. It was worked up as in method (b) for the preceding compound to give a solid which was crystallised from dil. ethanol to afford XVIII as clusters of colorless needles (1.4 g.; 40%), m.p. 245-246°, undepressed on admixture with the sample prepared in method (a).

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